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Research Article

**A STUDY ON ALPHA-1 ANTITRYPSIN DEFICIENCY: CAUSES,
SYMPTOMS AND TREATMENT****Senthilraja M., Monika K., Priyadharshini K., Suga Priya R., Preetha S., Kumutha K.,
P.S.V. College of Pharmaceutical Science and Research, Krishnagiri-635108.****Abstract:**

Alpha-1 Antitrypsin Deficiency (AATD) is a genetic disorder characterized by low levels or dysfunctional production of alpha-1 antitrypsin (AAT), a protease inhibitor primarily synthesized in the liver. AAT plays a critical role in protecting lung tissue from neutrophil elastase-mediated degradation. Deficiency of AAT predisposes individuals to early-onset pulmonary emphysema, particularly in the lower lobes, and may also lead to liver diseases such as cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma due to the accumulation of misfolded AAT in hepatocytes. AATD follows an autosomal codominant inheritance pattern, with the most common pathogenic variants being the Z and S alleles of the SERPINA1 gene. Diagnosis involves serum AAT level measurement, phenotyping, and genotyping. Management includes lifestyle modifications, augmentation therapy, pulmonary rehabilitation, and in severe cases, lung or liver transplantation. Early recognition of AATD is essential for optimal management and slowing disease progression.

Key words: *AIAD, Alpha-1 Antitrypsin Disorder, Serpin A1 Deficiency, Inherited Emphysema, Genetic COPD.*

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency (AATD), often referred as alpha-1 proteinase inhibitor deficiency, is a hereditary disorder that raises the risk of liver and lung disease among other illnesses¹. The archetypal member of the SERPine Protease INhibitors (SERPIN) superfamily and the main protease inhibitor in serum is alpha-1-antitrypsin (AAT)².

The majority of the individuals has normal levels of the protein in their bloodstream and carries two copies of the wild-type M allele of SERPINA1, which codes for AAT. AAT is produced in the liver and released into the bloodstream, where its main function is to shield lung tissue from neutrophil elastase-induced damage³.

FIGURE 1. INHERITANCE OF AATD

SERPINA1 gene, contains instructions for producing the AAT protein, is altered in AATD. AAT deficiency typically runs in families because these gene alterations are inherited from the parents⁴.

- Having two mutated copies of the gene indicates the AAT deficiency, increases the risk of lung disease or liver damage before the age of 45⁴.
- Having one mutated copy of the gene indicates that the individual acts as a carrier of AAT deficiency, slightly higher risk of lung disease, particularly if they have other risk factors like smoking and might transmit the mutated gene on to the children⁴.

An extremely underdiagnosed condition is AATD. It is believed that over 120,000 people in Europe suffer with severe AATD, and over 90% of them go undiagnosed⁵. The only particular treatment for AATD is infusion of plasma-derived AAT (augmentation therapy) to restore physiological levels⁶.

Table 1. EXPRESSION OF PHENOTYPE IN ALPHA-1 ANTITRYPSIN DEFICIENCY

PHENOTYPE	AATD SERUM LEVEL	RISK OF EMPHYSEMA
PI*SZ	75-120mg/Dl (8-16 micromol/L)	Slightly increased
PI*SS	100-200mg/Dl (15-33 micromol/L)	Minimally increased
PI*MM	150-3500mg/Dl (20-48 micromol/L)	Normal

NOTE: PI- The gene locus (Protease Inhibitor); * indicates a separator b/w the gene locus and the allele.

HISTORY:

FIGURE 2

AATD was firstly discovered by Carl-Bertil Laurell and Eriksson more than 50 years ago, in 1963, they noticed the absence of a protein band corresponding to AAT in the electrophoresis strips of plasma samples from several pulmonary emphysema cases³. It was discovered in 1970 that the genetic basis of AATD is an autosomal co-dominant condition brought on by mutations in the chromosome 14 SERPINA1 gene. AAT deficiency is caused by a few gene alterations:

1. Reduction in the quantity of AAT protein production in liver.
2. Stop the liver from producing any AAT.
3. Modifying the shape of the AAT protein so that it cannot leave the liver to protect your lungs.
4. Over time, AAT accumulates in the liver and damages it⁹.

TYPES:

1. Normal (MM GENOTYPE) :
2. Mild deficiency (MS GENOTYPE) :
3. Intermediate deficiency (MZ GENOTYPE) :
4. Moderate deficiency (SS GENOTYPE) :
5. Severe deficiency (ZZ GENOTYPE) :

2. AIM OF ALPHA-1 ANTITRYPSIN DEFICIENCY

The aim is to understand the pathophysiology, clinical manifestations, and to improve the diagnosis, treatment and management of Alpha-1 Antitrypsin Deficiency (AATD) in order to improve patient outcomes, quality of life and guide effective therapeutic strategies.

OBJECTIVE:

1. **Early Diagnosis:** Identify individuals with AATD through genetic testing and screening, particularly in those with a family history or symptoms suggestive of the condition.
2. **Optimize Treatment:** Provide effective treatment options, such as augmentation therapy, to slow disease progression and

manage symptoms.

3. **Symptom Management:** Develop strategies to manage respiratory and liver-related symptoms, improving patient comfort and functional capacity.
4. **Lifestyle Modifications:** Educate patients on lifestyle changes, such as smoking cessation and healthy nutrition, to support overall health and reduce disease progression.
5. **Research and Development:** Encourage research into new therapeutic approaches and treatments to improve outcomes for individuals with AATD.
6. **Patient Education and Support:** Provide patients and families with accurate information, support, and resources to manage the condition effectively.

3. ETIOLOGY

Alpha-1 Antitrypsin Deficiency is caused by mutations in the SERPINA1 gene. Genetic mutations in the highly polymorphic SERPINA1 can lead to alpha-1 antitrypsin (AAT) deficiency, an underlying genetic condition that can alter AAT's functionality and serum levels¹⁰. Defective AAT proteins can accumulate in the liver as a result of polymerization caused by certain SERPINA1 mutations. Liver disorders like cirrhosis may develop as a result of this buildup¹¹⁻¹².

The most common severe genotype is homozygous Pi*ZZ¹³, but 85% to 95% of people have the homozygous Pi*MM genotype, which results in normal levels (>20 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) of functional AAT¹⁴. In the general population, the three most common SERPINA1 protease inhibitor (Pi) alleles are M, which results in normal levels of functional AAT, and S and Z, which are linked to reduced AAT serum levels¹³. According to numerous research studies, Cigarette smoking is a major contributor to the loss in lung function¹⁰⁻¹⁶.

FIGURE 3. SMOKING LEADING TO AATD

AAT is less active in the blood and lungs as a result of impaired protein synthesis. Individuals may also develop liver disease, panniculitis, and vasculitis¹⁵.

In addition, between the ages of 20 and 50, abnormal

AAT can build up in the liver, resulting in lung conditions such bronchiectasis and emphysema as well as liver illness¹⁶.

FLOWCHART OF AATD MECHANISM:

4. PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

Reduced AAT concentrations cause lung disease, whereas changes in the AAT molecule's composition have been linked to AAT malfunction in liver disease¹⁷.

1. Genetic Basis:

The Z allele (Glu342Lys) is the most prevalent mutation that causes illness. The most common mutation linked to liver disease is the Z allele. It is brought on by a single amino acid substitution (Glu342Lys), known as a point mutation, which causes an abnormally folded protein¹⁸.

2. Pulmonary Basis:

People who have a history of smoking are more likely to develop emphysema and chronic

obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) if the lung tissues are destroyed¹⁹.

Cirrhosis of the liver might happen around age fifty²⁰. A level below the serum protective threshold of 11 micromol/L raises the chance of developing emphysema²¹.

3. Hepatic Basis:

Liver fibrosis is the result of persistent hepatic damage caused by a variety of liver illnesses, such as Hepatitis B, C, and fatty liver disease. In both adult and pediatric patients, fibrosis can also impact the results of liver transplantation and necessitate re-transplantation²².

FIGURE 4. SCHEMATIC REPRESENTATION OF AATD PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

4. Other organs:

Rarely, AATD can cause inflammatory damage from uncontrolled protease that affects other organs, such as the skin (e.g., panniculitis). Panniculitis is linked to alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency (AATD). Red, painful nodular lesions that frequently weep with an oily discharge and typically appear on the thighs, buttocks, and sites of physical trauma are clinical symptoms of panniculitis linked to AATD²³.

5. SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS

LUNGS:

- Shortness of breath (dyspnoea),
- Chronic cough with sputum,
- Fatigue or tiredness⁷.

LIVER:

- Yellowing of the skin and eyes (jaundice),
- Itching,
- Swelling in legs and abdomen (ascites),
- Throwing up blood.

OTHERS:

- Reduced exercise ability, Hypotension,
- Muscle cramp,
- Chest pain,
- Mild pain, Tachycardia⁷.

6. COMPLICATIONS:

LUNGS:

- Early onset of emphysema⁸,
- Chronic cough, wheezing, dyspnoea,
- Exacerbated by smoking or occupational exposures

LIVER:

- Liver Cirrhosis and liver failure in adolescents or adults,
- Increased risk of liver cancer,
- Neonatal hepatitis.

OTHERS:

- Panniculitis (inflammation of fat under the skin)
- Granulomatosis with polyangiitis (rarely).

Foods to be avoided: Processed meats, Smoking and tobacco, High-sugar foods, Foods high in saturated and Trans fats, Foods that trigger acid reflux.

Foods that may be beneficial: Antioxidant-rich foods, Omega-3 fatty acids, Whole grains.

7. DIAGNOSIS AND TEST OF ALPHA -1 ANTITRYPSIN DEFICIENCY

AATD is frequently underdiagnosed and requires attention and screening in particular patient groups.

DIAGNOSIS PROCESS:

1. Blood Test for AAT levels.
2. Genetic testing.
 - Protease Inhibitor (PI) typing.
 - DNA sequencing

3. Future evaluation.

- Clinical assessment.
- Lung function test.
- Liver function test⁴.

1. Blood Test: AAT blood testing may involve a blood test with blood from the arm or a finger prick. Some genetics tests involve a cheek swab. **For the Cheek swab,** a health care professional will wipe inside of the cheek with a small tool to remove some cells²⁵.

2. Genetic Testing:

- **Phenotyping:** Determines the specific type of AAT protein variant²⁴.
- **Genotyping:** Identifies the specific gene mutation of SERPINA1 gene causing AAT deficiency. Common mutations include S, Z, I, and F alleles²⁵.

3. Future Evaluation Test:

a. Liver Function Test: These test help to assess the health of the liver, as AAT deficiency can cause liver damage and liver cirrhosis²⁵.

b. Pulmonary Function Test: Spirometry and other pulmonary function tests are used to evaluate lung function and identify any airflow obstruction or emphysema associated with AAT deficiency²⁵. Spirometer (measuring lung capacity and airflow) helps to assess the lung function and monitor the progression of lung disease in individuals with AATD²⁵.

a. Clinical Assessment:

➤ **Medical History and Physical Examination:** A healthcare provider will enquire about the symptoms like shortness of breath, wheezing, chronic cough, and any family history of lung or liver disease, as AAT deficiency can manifest in both²⁵.

4. Imaging: Chest X-rays and CT scans can visualize lung damage, such as emphysema or bronchiectasis, which may indicate AAT deficiency²⁵.

8. TREATMENT AND MANAGEMENT

Rare AATD variants are characterized by reduced AAT plasma levels, variable intrahepatic accumulation, and associated with an increased risk of developing lung and/or liver disease²⁶. Cessation of smoking should be considered as a primary intervention that can improve outcomes²⁷. Some vaccinations are also recommended as a preventative measure for AATD and should follow local guidelines for people with COPD these may include interventions for influenza, COVID-19, respiratory syncytial virus, pneumococci, pertussis and shingles²⁸.

TYPES OF TREATMENT:

1. Augmentation therapy.

2. Medications.
3. Pulmonary rehabilitation.
4. Oxygen therapy.
5. Lung or Liver transplant.
6. Lifestyle changes.

1. AUGMENTATION THERAPY: Alpha-1 proteinase inhibitor (A1PI) derived from the human plasma is administered as an intravenously to increase the AAT levels in the lungs. To protect the lungs from further damage and to slow disease progression.

FIGURE 5. (A) AAT produced in the liver to protect the lungs from neutrophil elastase. **(B)** Z mutations in AAT gene, the $\alpha 1$ antitrypsin Z protein aggregates in the liver, resulting in low AAT concentrations in the lungs. **(C)** Progressive lung destruction resulting in emphysema.

2. MEDICATIONS:

- a) **Bronchodilators:** Helps to open airways for easier breathing and to manage respiratory symptoms.
- b) **Corticosteroids (inhaled or oral):** Reduces lung inflammation.
- c) **Antibiotics:** To treat respiratory infections quickly and to prevent the complications.
- d) **Vaccines:** Pneumococcal and annual influenza vaccines to prevent the infections.

3. PULMONARY REHABILITATION: A structured program involving exercise, nutrition advice, and education to improve lung function and quality of life.

4. OXYGEN THERAPY: Oxygen therapy is often used as a part of the treatment for Alpha-1 Antitrypsin Deficiency (AATD), particularly when the disease progresses to the point where it significantly impairs lung function.

5. LUNG OR LIVER TRANSPLANT: A **lung transplant** is a surgical procedure to replace one or both diseased lungs with healthy lungs from a diseased donor. A **Liver transplant** is a surgical procedure to replace a diseased liver with a healthy liver from a donor. For severe liver disease caused by **AAT** accumulation.

6. LIFESTYLE CHANGES: Cessation of smoking: Essential to slow lung damage. Avoid environmental pollutants: Dust, fumes, and chemicals. Healthy diet support overall health and lung function.

7. RESEARCH AND EMERGING THERAPIES:

a) GENE THERAPY:

Researchers are exploring gene therapy as potential treatment for AATD.

b) OTHER EMERGING THERAPIES:

Scientists are investigating new treatments such as small molecule therapies and RNA-based therapies.

FIGURE 6. FUTURE AATD THERAPIES
DRUGS USED TO TREAT AAT DEFICIENCY: Some currently marketed alpha-1 antitrypsin augmentation therapy approved by FDA includes the use of **PROLASTIN/PROLASTIN-C (Grifols)**, **ZEMAIRA (CSL Behring)**, **GLASSIA (Kamada/Takeda)**, **ARALAST (Takeda)**, and **ALFALASTIN (LFB Biotechnologies)**.

1. **PROLASTIN-C:** It is also known as Alpha-1-proteinase inhibitor (A1-PI) or alpha-1 antitrypsin (AAT). It is a purified human protein used to treat emphysema in patients with AAT Deficiency. It is a serine protease inhibitor that functions in the lungs to inhibit neutrophil elastase, a protein degrading enzyme.

FIGURE 7. PROLASTIN-C

2. **ARALAST NP:** ARALAST NP [Alpha-1-Proteinase Inhibitor (Human)] is a medicine used

to treat adults with lung diseases (emphysema) caused by severe Alpha1 Antitrypsin (AAT) Deficiency. ARALAST NP is not for use in lung disease other than severe Alpha1-PI deficiency.

FIGURE 8. ARALAST NP

9. CONCLUSION:

Alpha-1 Antitrypsin deficiency is a hereditary disorder with significant clinical implications, particularly affecting the lungs and liver. Early diagnosis is critical for preventing or delaying the progression of associated conditions such as emphysema and liver disease. Advances in diagnostic techniques and increased awareness have improved detection rates, while treatments like augmentation therapy and lifestyle changes offer symptom relief and improved quality of life. Ongoing research into gene therapy and novel therapeutics holds promise for more effective, long-term management. A comprehensive approach involving early screening, patient education, and multidisciplinary care is essential to optimizing outcomes for individuals with AATD.

10. REFERENCES

- Sandhaus RA, Turino G, Brantly ML, Campos M, Cross CE, Goodman K, Hogarth DK, Knight SL, Stocks JM, Stoller JK, Strange C. The diagnosis and management of alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency in the adult. *Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Diseases: Journal of the COPD Foundation*, 3(3), 2016; 668.
- Seixas, Susana, and Patricia Isabel Marques. "Known mutations at the cause of alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency an updated overview of SERPINA1 variation spectrum." *The application of clinical genetics*, 2021; 173-194.
- Strnad, P., McElvaney, N. G., & Lomas, D. A. Alpha1-antitrypsin deficiency. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 382(15),2020; 1443-1455.
- Vignola AM, Bonanno A, Profita M, Scichilone N, Scichilone N, Spatafora M, Bosquest J, Bonsignore G, Bellia V. Effect of age and asthma duration upon elastase and alpha-1 antitrypsin levels in adult asthmatics. *Eur Respir J*, 22,2003; 795-801.
- Torres-Durán, M., Lopez-Campos, J. L., Barrecheguren, M., Miravittles, M., Martínez-Delgado, B., Castillo, S., & Dasí, F. Alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency: Outstanding questions and future directions. *Orphanet journal of rare diseases*, 13, 2018; 1-15.
- Edgar, Ross G., Mitesh Patel, Susan Bayliss, Diana Crossley, Elizabeth Sapey, and Alice M. Turner. "Treatment of lung disease in alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency: a systematic review." *International journal of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease*, 2017; 1295-1308.
- Stoller JK, Aboussouan LS. A review of α 1-antitrypsin deficiency. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine*, 185(3), 2012; 246-59.
- Ranes, Justin, and James K. Stoller. "A review of alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency." In *Seminars in respiratory and critical care medicine*, vol. 26, no. 02, pp. 154-166. Copyright© 2005 by Thieme Medical Publishers, Inc., 333 Seventh Avenue, New York, NY 10001, USA., 2005
- Kueppers F. Clinical presentations of four patients with rare alpha 1 antitrypsin variants identified in a single US centre. *Respir Med Case Rep*, 20(32),2021; 101345.
- Foil KE. Variants of *SERPINA1* and the increasing complexity of testing for alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency. *Ther Adv Chronic Dis*, 12(2 Suppl.),2021; 33–48.
- Janciauskiene SM, Bals R, Koczulla R,. The discovery of α 1-antitrypsin and its role in health and disease. *Respir Med*, 105,2011; 1129–1139.
- Patel D, Teckman J. Liver disease with unknown etiology—have you ruled out alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency *Ther Adv Chronic Dis*, 12(2 Suppl.),2021; 25–32.
- Tejwani V, Stoller JK. The spectrum of clinical sequelae associated with alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency. *Ther Adv Chronic Dis*, 12(2 Suppl.), 2021.
- de Serres F, Blanco I. Role of alpha-1 antitrypsin in human health and disease. *J Intern Med*, 276, 2014; 311–335.
- Chorostowska-Wynimko J, Barrecheguren M, Ferrarotti I, et al. New patient-centric approaches to the management of alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis*, 15,2020; 345– 355.
- Miravittles, M.; Dirksen, A.; Ferrarotti, I.; Koblizek, V.; Lange, P.; Mahadeva, R.; McElvaney, N.G.; Parr, D.; Piitulainen, E.; Roche, N.,European Respiratory Society statement: Diagnosis and treatment of pulmonary diseases in alpha1-antitrypsin deficiency. *Eur.*

- Respir. J*, 50, 2017; 1700610.
17. MacDonald, Joanne L., and Carry E. Johnson. "Pathophysiology and treatment of α 1-antitrypsin deficiency." *American journal of health-system pharmacy*, 52.5, 1995; 481-489.
 18. Bouchecareilh M. Alpha-1 Antitrypsin Deficiency-Mediated Liver Toxicity: Why Do Some Patients Do Poorly? What Do We Know So Far? *Chronic obstrPulm Dis*, 7(3), 2020; 172-181.
 19. Kalfopoulos M, Wetmore K, ElMallah MK. Pathophysiology of Alpha-1 Antitrypsin Lung Disease. *Methods Mol Biol*, 1639, 2017; 9-19.
 20. Fregonese, Laura, and Jan Stolk. "Hereditary alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency and its clinical consequences." *Orphanet journal of rare diseases*, 3, 2008; 1-9.
 21. Stoller JK, Aboussouan LS. Alpha1-antitrypsin deficiency. *Lancet*, 1,365(9478), 2005; 2225-36.
 22. Berumen, Jennifer,. "Liver fibrosis: Pathophysiology and clinical implications." *WIREs mechanisms of disease*, 13.1, 2021; 1499.
 23. Stoller, James K., and Melissa Piliang. "Panniculitis in alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency: a review." *Clinical Pulmonary Medicine*, 15.2, 2008; 113-117.
 24. Committee the NA-1 AR. Guidelines for the diagnosis and management of α 1-antitrypsin deficiency
 25. Perlmutter DH: Alpha -1-antirypsin deficiency: diagnosis and treatment. *Clin Liver Dis*, 8, 2004 ;839- 859.
 26. Ottaviani S, Bartoli G, Carroll TP, Gangemi F, Balderacchi AM, Barzon V, et al. Comprehensive clinical diagnostic pipelines reveal new variants in alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency. *Am J Respir Cell Mol Biol*, 69(3), 2023; 355-366.
 27. Global Initiation for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD).Global strategy for prevention, diagnosis and management of COPD: 2024 report, <https://goldcopd.org/2024-gold-report/> (2024, accessed October 2024).
 28. Gadek JE, Fells GA, Zimmerman RL, Rennard SI, Crystal RG. Antielastases of the human alveolar structure: implications for the protease-antiprotease theory of emphysema. *J Clin Invest*, 68, 1981; 889-98.